

Synthetic Studies in Diterpene Series. Part X¹. A Synthesis of 2-Oxygenated (\pm)-Podocarpa-8,11,13- triene by Transposition of Ketonic Function

DHANONJOY NASIPURI* and SATINATH BANERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

Carbanions generated *in situ* through de-ethoxycarbonylation of ethyl 2-cyano-3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (11) and ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (7) by heating with lithium chloride in hexamethylphosphorus triamide according to Krapcho have been submitted respectively to alkylation reaction with phenethyl bromide and to Michael addition with 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one with a view to utilising the resultant 5-cyano-4,4-dimethyl-7-phenylheptan-2-one (10) for a convenient synthesis of 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-trienes (6). The yields of the reactions are, however, poor (15-20%), presumably due to adverse steric effect of the *geminal* methyl groups in the reactants. Use of sodium hydride under phase transfer catalysis considerably improves the yield of alkylation reaction (with the keto group in 11 protected by cyclic acetal formation) and the product (14) undergoes de-ethoxycarbonylation; but the resultant nitrile (15) is found to be resistant to hydrolysis leading to an impasse.

2-Oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (20) is finally synthesised from the easily accessible 3-oxo-derivative (18) by transposition of the ketonic function through a two step process, namely oxidation with molecular oxygen in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide to 2,3-dioxo-derivative and its subsequent reduction with boiling hydriodic acid. The ketone (20) on treatment with lithium aluminium hydride affords 2 β (axial) and 2 α (equatorial) alcohols in a 60 : 40 ratio.

PODOCARPA-8,11,13-triene (1) forms the skeletal structure of a number of naturally occurring ring C-aromatic tricyclic diterpenes and has been synthesised by different groups of workers of which the following may be mentioned: (i) Robinson-Mannich base ring homologation of 3,4-dihydro-1-methylnaphthalen-2(1*H*)-ones followed by dimethylation of the resultant α,β -unsaturated tricyclic ketones and catalytic hydrogenation^{2,3} which gives 3-oxopodocarpatrienes (2), useful for synthesis of 3-oxygenated di- and tri-terpenoids; (ii) cyclisation of 1-phenethyl-2,6,6-trimethylcyclohexanols (3, OH at 1-, 2-, and 3-) and their cyclohexene equivalents⁴, an old method recently renovated and improved by Davis *et al.*⁵ (use of methane sulphonic acid-phosphorus pentoxide increasing the yield and stereoselectivity); and finally, (iii) a biogenetic-type of cyclisation of 6(*E*)-9-aryl-2,6-dimethylnona-2,6-dienes (4)⁶ under acid catalysis. Very recently, Bhattacharya and Mukherjee⁷ have worked out a synthesis of *cis* 13-methoxy-1-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene starting from a naphthalene derivative and using Birch reduction as a reductive methylation step. In contrast, synthesis of 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene system (6) is virtually unknown except for a recent short report by Davis and Johnson⁸ who have used copper(I) catalysed 1,6-conjugate addition of methoxybenzylmagnesium chlorides to 4-methylene-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone⁹ for the synthesis of cyclohexenones (5) and cyclised them by phosphoric acid into a mixture of 5 α - and 5 β -2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-trienes (6) in a 50 : 50 ratio.

As a part of a programme undertaken in our laboratory for the synthesis of natural products related to diterpenes¹⁰ and furanosesquiterpenes¹¹, we were interested in developing a simple synthesis of the 2-oxopodocarpatriene system (6) and subsequently utilising it for a total synthesis of salviol, a diterpenoid alcohol with 2 α -hydroxy group in a podocarpatriene skeleton, isolated a few years back from *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge¹² (see our synthesis of miltirone¹³ isolated from the same species). Our strategy was to prepare the cyclohexenones (5) through a simple sequence of reactions involving

Chart 1

Michael addition of ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate to 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (mesityl oxide), conversion of the adduct to 5,5-dimethyl-4-phenethyl-

cyclohexa-1,3-dione (9) (Scheme 1A), reaction of methylmagnesium iodide with the derived isobutyl enol ether¹⁴ and acidic hydrolysis to the cyclohexenone (5). The Michael addition, however, did not go even under phase transfer catalysis, a method which we have very successfully used¹⁵ for such reactions using a variety of donor and acceptor molecules. The only product we got was the cyanodiketone (8) which could not be hydrolysed without disrupting the 1,3-dione moiety. In the present communication, we wish to present our results on the generation of carbanions from substituted cyanoacetic esters using Krapcho's technique¹⁶ (heating with lithium halides in hexmethylphosphorus triamide) and their reactions with Michael acceptors and alkylating agents giving an alternative route to the aforementioned synthon. We also report a clean synthesis of 2-oxopodocarpatriene (20) from the easily accessible 3-oxo-derivative (18) by the transposition of the ketonic function.

Encouraged by these observations, we subjected ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (7) under the same condition in presence of 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (Scheme 1B) with the hope that the intermediate α -cyanocarbanion, stripped off the ethoxycarbonyl group and so sterically less hindered and more reactive, would undergo facile Michael addition. Similarly, ethyl 2-cyano-3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (11) was allowed to alkylate intermolecularly with phenethyl bromide by heating the reactants with lithium chloride in HMPTA. In both the cases, the expected product, 5-cyano-4,4-dimethyl-7-phenylheptan-2-one (10) was formed but the yields were discouragingly low (15-20%) and the product was contaminated with some amides (ν_{\max} 2250, 1718 and 1670 cm^{-1}) presumably due to partial hydrolysis of the cyano group. The major products were those arising out of de-ethoxycarbonylation of the starting cyanoesters. Apparently, the unreactivity of 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (steric reason)

Scheme 1

Alkylation of the intermediate carbanions in the dealkoxycarbonylation of β -oxoesters, geminal diesters and α -cyanoesters by lithium halides in HMPTA has been carried out successfully both intramolecularly^{17,18} and intermolecularly¹⁹. Thus 2-acetobutyrolactone when heated with LiCl in HMPTA affords cyclopropyl methyl ketone (intramolecular decarboxylative alkylation)¹⁷. Substituted malonic and cyanoacetic esters under similar conditions give mono- and di-alkylated products with alkyl halides accompanied by the loss of a carboethoxyl group (intermolecular alkylation)¹⁹. A large number of spiro-compounds have also been synthesised¹⁸ from substrates containing both a carboethoxyl group and an alkylating side chain.

and of phenylethyl bromide as an alkylating agent (electronic reason) is responsible for the poor yield. Alkylation of the cyanoester (11) with benzyl chloride under identical condition afforded mono- and di-benzylated products with the loss of ethoxycarbonyl group in 20 and 30% yields, respectively. The yields in all these reactions were not optimised; further study in this direction was abandoned.

A final attempt was made for the alkylation of the substituted cyanoesters (11) and (12) with phenylethyl bromide using sodium hydride and aliquat 336 (tricaprylmethylammonium chloride)²⁰. In the first case, the product was a crystalline solid isolated in 75% yield which turned out to be the enol ether (13) (Scheme 1C), obviously formed by

an initial Claisen condensation followed by *O*-alkylation. In the second case, the desired cyano-ester (**14**) was obtained in 45% yield and was smoothly de-ethoxycarbonylated by Krapcho's method. But the resultant cyano-cyclic ketal (**15**) was found to be resistant to hydrolysis leading to another impasse.

All these attempts having failed, we ultimately took resort to transpose the ketonic function in the easily accessible 3-oxo-podocarpa-8,11,13-triene (**18**) from C-3 to C-2. A large number of methods for such transposition are available depending on the nature of the substrates²¹. Of these we selected the one used for substituted cyclohexanones having

the normal value (δ 1.00) when the ketone (**20**) is reduced to a mixture of alcohols. The mass spectrum of **20** shows specific fragmentations which are discussed in Scheme 3. It differs from that of the 3-oxo-derivative (**18**) in three important aspects: (i) while the spectrum of 2-oxo-compound gives specific fragmentation pattern easily assignable, that of 3-oxo-compound has too many non-specific fragmentations, (ii) the peak at *m/e* 143 in **20** (base peak) is much more intense because of its origin from at least three pathways (Scheme 3) while that in **18** is weak, and (iii) the spectrum of 3-oxo-derivative shows a peak at *m/e* 157, homologous with **23** of *m/e* 143 as expected.

Scheme 2

a quaternary α -carbon which are oxidised²² by molecular oxygen in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide to α -diketones and then reduced to the isomeric β -quaternary ketone. Accordingly, the tricyclic ketone (**16**)²³ (Scheme 2) was dimethylated²⁴ to **17**, the latter hydrogenated²⁵ to the *trans* 3-oxo-derivative (**18**) along with some *cis* isomer²⁶ (10-15% as determined by glc and ¹H nmr²⁷). The ketone (**18**) was converted into the diketone (**19**) by oxygenation in basic media and the latter reduced by boiling 47% hydriodic acid to furnish a mixture of two products, the major (the first peak in glc) being the desired 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (**20**) (50%) obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 88-90°. The minor contaminant might be 2-hydroxy-3-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene and was easily separated out by column chromatography. The 2-oxo-derivative (**20**) showed the ¹H nmr spectrum δ (CDCl₃) 7.50-7.08 (4H, m, 4 \times ArH), 2.90 (2H, m, 7-H₂), 2.55 (2H, m, 1-H₂), 2.22 (2H, q, 3-H₂), 1.90 (1H, m, 5 α -H), 1.50-1.20 (2H, m, 6-H₂), 1.33 (3H, s, 10-Me), 1.10 (3H, s, 4 α -Me) and 0.60 (3H, s, 4 β -Me). The methylene multiplets and quartets were partly superimposed so that accurate *J* values could not be calculated. The chemical shift of 4-axial methyl protons is unusually upfield and may be due to the anisotropic shielding of the carbonyl group^{28,29}, an effect perhaps accentuated by 1,3-diaxial interaction between methyl groups. The signal comes down to

Scheme 3

The ketone (**20**) was next reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in ether affording a mixture of 2 β -ol (**21**) (60%) and 2 α -ol (**22**) (40%). The axial attack leading to equatorial alcohol (**22**) is sterically hindered (see reduction of 3,3,5-trimethylcyclohexa-

none)³⁰ by two axial methyl groups at C-4 and C-10 and this explains the preponderance of the axial alcohol (21) in the reduction. The ratio of the epimeric alcohols in the mixture was determined by glc and supported by ¹H nmr spectra which show the methine proton (CHOH) as multiplets at δ 3.77 and 4.13 for equatorial and axial alcohols, respectively in 40 : 60 ratio. Pure equatorial (2 α -ol) alcohol may be obtained by equilibration of the dichloroalumino derivatives of mixed alcohols³¹. Experiments towards a total synthesis of salviol following this procedure is in progress.

Experimental

All melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer 237 B infra-cord spectrophotometer, in CHCl₃, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 390 90 MHz machine in CDCl₃ using SiMe₄ as internal standard, and mass spectra with Hitachi RMU-6L spectrometer at 70-80 eV using direct inlet system. Glc was done on a Varian 3700 gas chromatograph using both FFAP (15%) and Carbowax 20M (10%) columns (6' \times 1/8") using flame ionisation detector and with N₂ as carrier gas. Light petroleum refers to the fraction b.p. 40-60°. All organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Tlc was done in 20 \times 20 cm plates with 0.1 mm layers of silica gel G.

Ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (7) : To the sodiosalt prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (45.2 g, 0.4 mol) and sodium (4.6 g, 0.2 mol) in dry ethanol (100 ml), was added phenethyl bromide (37.0 g, 0.2 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 12 h. The excess of alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the product worked up in the usual way to furnish ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (7) (31 g, 79%), b.p. 163-167°/7 mm; ν_{\max} 2250 (CN) and 1750 cm⁻¹ (CO₂Et). Attempt to prepare 7 by alkylating ethyl cyanoacetate with phenethyl bromide by heating with anhydrous K₂CO₃ and benzyltriethylammonium chloride (BTEAC) in benzene¹⁵ gave only 35-40% of the product.

Ethyl 2-cyano-3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (11) : Ethyl 2-cyano-3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate was prepared from 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one and ethyl cyanoacetate by adopting the general procedure of Michael condensation with phase transfer catalyst (BTEAC)¹⁵ in 93% yield. It had b.p. 140°/10 mm.

5-Cyano-4,4-dimethyl-7-phenylheptan-2-one (10) : (A) By de-ethoxycarbonylative alkylation—A mixture of ethyl 2-cyano-3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (11) (10.5 g, 0.05 mol), anhydrous lithium chloride (1.9 g, 0.05 mol) and dry HMPTA (40 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 150° under nitrogen. When evolution of carbon dioxide ceased (1 h), phenethyl bromide (18.5 g, 0.1 mol) was added dropwise and the mixture stirred at 160° for 6 h. The solution turned into a yellowish red viscous liquid which was cooled, diluted with water, extracted with ether (2 \times 100 ml), the ethereal extract washed thoroughly

with water and dried. The residue on evaporation of solvent was distilled *in vacuo*. After an initial low-boiling fraction, (upto 130°/10 mm), a viscous oil was obtained (2.4 g, 20%), b.p. 160-175°/0.5 mm (Found : C, 78.5; H, 8.9; N, 5.5. C₁₆H₂₁NO requires C, 79.01; H, 8.64; N, 5.76%); ν_{\max} 2250, 1710 and 1670 cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr spectrum was more or less consistent with the structure barring two or three extra peaks.

(B) By *in situ* Michael addition—The above experiment was repeated under similar condition with phenethyl bromide replaced by 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (4.9 g, 0.05 mol). The product on usual work-up and distillation afforded two fractions, (i) b.p. 80-85°/0.4 mm, identified as γ -phenylpropyl cyanide by hydrolysis to γ -phenylbutyric acid, and (ii) b.p. 160-170°/0.4 mm (1.8 g, 15%). The latter was identical (ir) with the one (10) described above.

Benzylation of 5-cyano-4,4-dimethyl-7-phenylheptan-2-one : A mixture of the cyanoester (11) (8.4 g, 0.04 mol), lithium chloride (1.52 g, 0.04 mol) and HMPTA (20 ml) was heated at 160° for 1 h under nitrogen. Benzyl chloride (5.04 g, 0.04 mol) was added and heating continued for 4 h at 160°. The product on usual work-up afforded 5-cyano-4,4-dimethyl-6-phenylhexan-2-one (1.84 g, 20%), b.p. 135-140°/0.2 mm (Found : C, 78.1; H, 8.0. C₁₅H₁₉NO requires C, 78.6; H, 8.3%); ν_{\max} 2230 and 1705 cm⁻¹. The higher boiling fraction gave 5-benzyl-5-cyano-4,4-dimethyl-6-phenylhexan-2-one (3.8 g, 30%) (Found : C, 82.25; H, 7.50. C₂₂H₂₅NO requires C, 82.75; H, 7.80%); ν_{\max} 2200 and 1710 cm⁻¹.

Alkylation of cyano-ester (11) with phenethyl bromide under phase transfer catalysis : A suspension of sodium hydride (2.5 g, 50% dispersion in oil, 0.05 mol) in a mixture of benzene (50 ml) and dimethylformamide (50 ml) was treated with the cyano-ester (11) (10.55 g, 0.05 mol) until evolution of H₂ ceased. Aliquat 336 (1.25 g, 0.0025 mol) in benzene (5 ml) was next added followed by phenethyl bromide (9.25 g, 0.05 mol) and the mixture refluxed with stirring for 20 h. The cooled solution was decomposed with 1 N HCl, the organic layer separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (2 \times 100 ml). The combined ethereal extract was washed successively with aqueous NaHCO₃ and H₂O, dried and solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation afforded a solid (11.1 g, 75%), b.p. 195-205°/0.5 mm, which crystallised from methanol in colourless plates, m.p. 107-109° and identified as 4-cyano-5,5-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-3-yloxyphenethyl ether (13) (Found : C, 75.7; H, 7.1; N, 5.5. C₁₇H₁₉NO₂ requires C, 75.8; H, 7.1; N, 5.2%); ν_{\max} 2240 and 1680 cm⁻¹; δ 7.33 (5H, m, 5 \times ArH), 5.43 (1H, s, 2-H), 4.07 (2H, t, J 7Hz, OCH₂), 3.29 (1H, s, 4-H), 3.00 (2H, t, J 7Hz, CH₂Ph), 2.30 (2H, s, 6-H₂), and 1.23 and 1.17 (3H \times 2, 2 \times s, 2 \times CH₃).

Ketalisation of cyano-ester (11) : A mixture of the cyano-ester (11) (21.1 g, 0.1 mol), ethylene

glycol (6.2 g, 0.1 mol), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (500 mg) and benzene (125 ml) was refluxed with azeotropic separation of water for 20 h. The usual work-up afforded the cyclic ketal (**12**) (20.4 g, 80%), b.p. 135°/8 mm; ν_{\max} 2240 (CN) and 1735 cm^{-1} (CO_2Et); δ 4.30 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, OCH_2), 4.1 (1H, s, CH), 4.02 (4H, s, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}$), 1.98 (2H, s, CH_2) and 1.35 - 1.22 (12H, m, $4 \times \text{CH}_3$).

Alkylation of cyclic ketal (12) under phase transfer catalysis: To a suspension of sodium hydride (1.92 g, 50%) in benzene (80 ml) and dimethylformamide (80 ml) was added the ketal (**12**) (10.2 g, 0.04 mol). When the formation of the sodium salt was complete, Aliquat 336 (1.25 g) was introduced in the mixture followed by phenethyl bromide (7.4 g, 0.04 mol). After reflux for 20 h under nitrogen with stirring, the product was decomposed with water containing a few drops of acetic acid, the organic layer separated and the aqueous phase extracted once with benzene. The combined benzene layer was washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 , dried and distilled. The product (**14**) was collected (6.5 g, 45%), b.p. 160-180°/0.4 mm (Found: C, 69.7; H, 8.5. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_4$ requires C, 70.2; H, 8.1%); ν_{\max} 2230 (CN) and 1735 cm^{-1} (CO_2Et); δ 7.31 (5H, br. s, $5 \times \text{ArH}$), 4.30 (2H, q, OCH_2), 4.00 (4H, s, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}$), 3.00 (2H, t, PhCH_2), 1.94 (2H, s, CH_2), 1.70 (2H, m, CH_2) and 1.33 - 1.10 (12H, m, $4 \times \text{CH}_3$).

De-ethoxycarbonylation of cyano-ester (14). A mixture of the above ketal-cyanoester (**14**) (6.0 g, 0.017 mol), lithium chloride (0.65 g, 0.017 mol) and HMPTA (20 ml) was heated at 160° in an oil-bath under N_2 for 3 h till no more CO_2 evolved. The product on usual work-up and distillation afforded the de-ethoxycarbonylated product (**15**) (4.2 g, 85%), b.p. 140-150°/0.5 mm (Found: C, 74.8; H, 8.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 75.3, H, 8.7%); ν_{\max} 2225 cm^{-1} (CN).

3-Oxopodocarpa-5,8,11,13-tetraene (17) The tricyclic ketone (**16**), m.p. 91°, was prepared from 3,4-dihydro-1-methylnaphthalen-2(1*H*)-one by the usual method²³. To a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide prepared from potassium (1.6 g, 0.043 mol) and dry *t*-butanol (75 ml) was added a solution of the ketone (**16**) (3.1 g, 0.145 mol) in benzene (5 ml). A reddish colour appeared; methyl iodide (10.3 g) was added and the mixture stirred overnight at ambient temperature. It was then decomposed with water and a few drops of HCl, the organic matter extracted with ether, dried and distilled. A viscous oil obtained (2.5 g, 70%), b.p. 160-165°/1 mm was purified by chromatography over silica gel (100 g). Although glc of the purified sample gave a single peak, the compound (**17**) could not be crystallised (Found: C, 84.8; H, 8.6. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 85.0; H, 8.33%); ν_{\max} 1705 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.30 (4H, m, $4 \times \text{ArH}$), 6.0 (1H, t, J 4.5 Hz, 6H), 3.40 (2H, d J 4.5 Hz, 7-H_2), 2.70-2.20 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$) and 1.32, 1.23 and 1.13 (9H, $3 \times \text{s}$, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$).

3-Oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (18): The foregoing unsaturated ketone (**17**) (2.0 g) in ethanol

(30 ml) was shaken in an atmosphere of H_2 with palladium-charcoal (500 mg) for 10 h during which time theoretical amount of H_2 was absorbed. The catalyst was filtered off and the resultant 3-oxopodocarpa-triene (**18**) was worked up and distilled (1.8 g), b.p. 135-145°/0.5 mm. Glc and ^1H nmr showed it to be a mixture of 5α (>80%) and 5β (<20%) isomers. It was purified by column chromatography over silica gel when 5α -isomer was obtained (1.00 g) (Found: C, 84.0, H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.3; H, 9.1%); ν_{\max} 1705 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.30 (4H, m, $4 \times \text{ArH}$), 2.88 (2H, t, 7-H_2), 2.53 (2H, m, 2-H_2), 2.00-1.30 (5H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2 + \text{CH}$) and 1.23-1.07 (9H, $3 \times \text{s}$, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$); m/e 242 (M^+), 227, 185, 157, 143 and 129 (peaks with lower m/e values not given).

2-Oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (20): (A) Oxidation of the 3-oxoderivative—The foregoing ketone (**18**) (0.4 g) in dry *t*-butanol (40 ml) containing potassium *t*-butoxide made to 1 *N* was shaken in oxygen for 20 min. Water (5 ml) and acetic acid (5 ml) were added and *t*-butanol was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with aqueous NaHCO_3 , 20% KOH and H_2O , dried and solvent removed to furnish the diketone (**19**) as an oily residue (0.4 g) which was submitted to the next operation without further purification.

(B) Reduction of the dioxo-compound (**19**)—The above diketone (**19**) was heated with a refluxing mixture of glacial acetic acid (25 ml) and aqueous HI (47%, 5 g) for 2 h. The mixture was diluted with water, the organic matter taken up in ether, the ethereal solution washed with aqueous NaOH, dried and solvent removed. The dark-coloured residue was passed through a column of silica gel and analysed by glc which showed two peaks with 70:30 ratio having retention times of 32 and 39 min, respectively (FFAP column at 220°). The two components were easily separated by column chromatography using silica gel and the first eluent was identified as 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (**20**) (120 mg), m.p. 88-90° (Found: C, 84.1; H, 9.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.3; H, 9.1%); ν_{\max} 1710 cm^{-1} . The ^1H nmr and mass spectra have been already discussed.

Reduction of 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (20): The above ketone (50 mg) was added to an ethereal solution (1 ml, 1 *M*) of LiAlH_4 . After agitation for 0.5 h, the solution was decomposed with cold 4 *N* H_2SO_4 and the product taken up in ether. On removal of the solvent, the mixture of 2β (**21**) and 2α (**22**) alcohols was obtained as a colourless gum. It was analysed by glc, the results of which have already been discussed. No attempt was made at this stage to separate the two epimeric alcohols. The mixture showed ^1H nmr spectrum as follows: δ 7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 4.13 (0.6H, m, 2-H_2), 3.77 (0.4H, m, 2-H_2), 2.80 (2H, m, 7-H_2), 2.30-1.80 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.82-1.30 (3H, m, $\text{CH}_3 + \text{CH}$) and 1.25-1.00 (9H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.B.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for a Senior Fellowship. The authors wish to record their thanks to Dr. Esak Ali, I.I.C.B., Calcutta for helping in the mass spectral analysis. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded by Shri N. P. Daw, Department of Chemistry, I.I.T., Kharagpur.

References

1. Part-IX, D. NASIPURI, I. DE DALAI and D. N. ROY, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1973, 1754.
2. K. RAMAN and P. N. RAO, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 294; see also E. C. DU FRU, F. J. MCQUILLIN and R. ROBINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53.
3. G. STORK, A. MEISELS and J. E. DAVIES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3419.
4. T. MATSUMOTO and S. USUI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, 52, 212.
5. B. W. AXON, B. R. DAVIS and P. D. WOODGATE, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1981, 2956 and references therein.
6. D. NASIPURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 407; D. NASIPURI, R. BHATTACHARYA and C. K. GHOSH, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 782.
7. S. BHATTACHARYA and D. MUKHERJEE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 4175.
8. B. R. DAVIS and S. J. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 614.
9. B. R. DAVIS and S. J. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1979, 2940.
10. D. NASIPURI and M. GUHA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4248; D. NASIPURI and I. DE DALAI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1976, 19.
11. D. NASIPURI and G. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1979, 2776.
12. T. HAYASHI, T. HANDA, M. OHASHI, K. KAKISAWA, HONG-YEN HSU and YUH PAN CHEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 541.
13. D. NASIPURI and A. K. MITRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1973, 285.
14. G. PYNE, R. C. BANERJEE and D. NASIPURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 199; R. L. FRANK, R. ARMSTRONG, J. KWIATEK and H. A. PRICE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1979.
15. S. BANERJEE, M. DATTA GUPTA, A. SARKAR and D. NASIPURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 1168.
16. A. P. KRAPCHO, J. F. WEIMASTER, J. M. ELDRIDGE, E. G. E. JAHNGEN, A. J. LOVEY and W. P. STEPHENS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 138.
17. S. TAKEI and Y. KAWANO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 4389.
18. R. G. EILERMAN and B. J. WILLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1981, 30.
19. A. MORIO, M. KAZUTOSHI and T. HISASHI, *Chem. Lett.*, 1975, 1149.
20. H. D. DURST and L. LIEBESKIND, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, 39, 3271.
21. F. M. HAUSER and S. PRASANNA, *Synthesis*, 1980, 621; E. J. COREY and J. E. RICHMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 5276; B. M. TROST, K. HIROI and S. KUNOSUMI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 97, 438; W. E. FRISTAD, T. R. BAILLY and L. A. PAQUETTE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 162; J. A. MARSHALL and H. ROEBKE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, 34, 4188 and references therein.
22. W. REUSCH and R. LEMAHIEU, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3068; E. BAILLY, D. H. B. BARTON, J. ELKS and J. F. TEMPLETON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1578.
23. K. D. ZWAHLEN, W. J. HORTON and G. FUJIMOTO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 3131.
24. M. YANAGITA, M. HIRAKURA and F. SEKI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 841.
25. H. J. RINGOLD and G. ROSENKRANZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 602.
26. Y. TACHIBANA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, 48, 298.
27. M. FETIZON and G. MOREAU, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1965, 3479.
28. L. M. JACKMAN and S. STERNHELL, "Applications of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1969, p. 243.
29. D. NASIPURI, A. K. SAMADDAR and G. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 727.
30. P. T. LANSBURY and R. E. MACLEAY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 1940.
31. E. L. ELIEL and D. NASIPURI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 3809.
32. See also M. FETIZON and J. DELOBELLE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1961, 1632.